

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Ismael****FIRST NAME: Gomez****PROGRAM CODE: DCTD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Dr Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The Author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago footnote (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The Author did use Zotero to insert references

The Author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 2%

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2016 on Windows 10 pro)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. What is the concept of a research proposal?

- Ethical considerations, submissions, funding detailed methodology,
- Statement of purpose, research questions, relevant literature review, methodology, and possible study impact.¹**
- A detailed outline of the study, methodology feasibility, identified problem, analysis
- Topic, introduction, research questions, bibliography.

¹ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019), 220.

2. **What are the components of an excellent literature review?**

- Excessive information on a particular topic gathered from Wikipedia is credible enough for an excellent literature review.
- A literature review documents a detailed review of past research. It summarises known facts to determine what is unknown concerning the research topic and arguments in the literature and provides study rationale.²**
- This critical activity allows for a brief understanding of the research activity and the projected input of the study.
- It is a paraphrase compilation of all recognised published work related to the study.

3. **Describe the component of scholarly written methodology?**

- Design justification, design paraphrase, data collection and analysis, study design.
- The rationale for the research design, physical research settings, population sample, data source collection and analysis method, limitations and boundaries.³**

² Ibid., 70–80.

³ Ibid., 80–85.

- Focus groups, one-on-one interviews, case studies, qualitative observation and ethnographic research.
- Brief description of the methods, equipment and procedures, the limitations encountered, sample collection and data analysis.

4. **What are the significant ways of representing infographics?**

- Tables, charts, infographics, text.
- Tables, graphs, charts, plots.⁴**
- Tables, figures, data, graphs.
- Tables, figures, data, text.

5. **After a well-written article, how do you link the research proposal, questions, and findings to a logical point?**

- The conclusion replicates the results section, highlights the study's salient findings, outlines the outcomes of your research, and acknowledges the study's limitations to avoid further questioning.
- The conclusion provides an elaborate and ample discussion of the research by linking all chapters of the article.

⁴ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 80–100.

- It is the ending part of a research paper. It explains the findings in simple terms, which will help the reader understand the significance of the research. The content may include new information.
 - ☑ **The conclusion chapter establishes the study finding integration, findings, and analysis with strong, clear, consistent, and concise messages for the reader.⁵**
6. **How best can you summarise the whole research in a written article of about 500 words?**
- The abstract gives initial impressions of a research article, accurate and meticulously drafted, with detailed findings and conclusions.
 - ☑ **Abstracts are generally within a defined word count. The abstract summarizes the study, including the problem statement, purpose, scope, data sources, methodology, essential findings, and inference.⁶**
 - An abstract is a very brief portion of an article that includes speciality jargon that may be difficult to read and even harder to understand.

⁵ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 87–89.

⁶ Turabian, 1110–1115.

- The abstract should detail your entire project and be written before the rest of the paper.

7. **According to the WHO style guide, how are dates formatted?**

- Day Month, Year
- Month-Day-Year
- Day-Month (in number)-Year
- Day Month (spelt in full) Year.⁷**

8. **Using the Turabian Author-Date citation style, how do you reference a single-authored book?**

- Author's last name, Author's first name, Date (parentheses), Title (quotation mark), Editor(s)/Translator(s), Place, Publication Press.
- Author's first name Author's last name. Edition. Date. Title (underlined). Editor(s)/Translator(s). Place: Publication Press.
- Author's last name, Author's first name, Edition (if existing). Date. Title (italics). Editor(s)/Translator(s) (if existing). Place: Publication Press.⁸**

⁷ World Health Organization, *WHO Editorial Style Manual* (Geneva: World Health Organization, 1993), 52.

⁸ Turabian, 136.

- Author's last name, Author's first name, Date (in parentheses), Title, Editor(s)/Translator(s), Place, Publication Press.

9. **How should numbers be written when they are part of the text (not as a citation)?**

- All numbers are written in figures.
- All numbers are spelt out unless used in a specific numerical context or a series of numbers.
- Numbers are written in either numbers or figures depending on what audience one writes for (e.g., numbers in scientific research papers are always written in figures).
- Numbers less than ten are spelt out. Numbers 10 and higher are written in figures unless used in a specific numerical context or a series of numbers.⁹**

10. **How is a quotation written in line with UK English with regards to quotation marks?**

- The quotation starts with inverted commas; the quotation within this is in quotation mark

⁹ WHO, *WHO Editorial Style Manual*, 52.

- The quotation starts with quotation marks; the quotation within this is put in inverted commas.¹⁰**
- Inverted commas are used by both parties
- Quotation marks are used for both

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019.

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¹⁰ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 4th ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 35.